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Global Lessons Learned from England’s National Institute for Health and Care Excellence A Possible Prescription for Higher Quality and Affordable Healthcare for all Americans

Healthcare costs in the United States are currently skyrocketing toward an unsustainable future. It is predicted that as the aging American population continues to increase, Medicare will become insolvent. However, creating a sustainable healthcare system in the United States that is cost-effective yet efficient, seems like a daunting endeavor. To gain insight and perspective on what can be done to improve the delivery of our healthcare, one only must look across the pond to England. Through the establishment of the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE), England has been able to provide quality care in a cost-effective manner. Lessons learned from England’s National Institute for Health and Care Excellence provide an example of how healthcare in the United States might be provided to a larger number of its citizens at a higher quality and lower overall cost.

The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) is an independent British organization established in 1999. The purpose of NICE is to “Provide national

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guidance and advice to improve health and social care.”¹ It produces a single set of standards, recommendations, and quality measures regarding aspects of healthcare. After evaluating the cost and efficiency of treatments, medications or screening procedures, NICE establishes guidelines for healthcare providers in England. “NICE has established a worldwide reputation for producing authoritative, evidence-based advice and guidelines.”²

NICE is responsible for creating quality standards not only for medical treatment, but also issues related to public health and social care.¹ NICE quality standards are designed to drive measurable quality improvements within a particular area of health or social care through devised concise statements.³ Some examples of quality standards that NICE has developed or is currently working on include acute heart failure, preventing harmful alcohol use in the community, suicide prevention, cerebral palsy, and children’s attachment.⁴ These are just a few of the many topics associated with quality standards that NICE has or will develop in the future.

The topics for these quality standards stem from referrals by different government organizations in England. For example, topics dealing with healthcare are submitted from the National Health Service England (NHS), public health topics from the Department of Health and social care issues from the Department of Health and Department for Education.⁵ The NICE quality standards team generates a topic overview for each quality standard referred from these various government organizations. This process enables many standards to be recommended by large government departments not always

associated with medical care, but indirectly affected by it.

Once a topic has been submitted and accepted by NICE, registered stakeholders are invited to convey their ideas for quality improvement.⁶ Stakeholders are essentially from organizations “registered with NICE because they have an interest in the topic, or they represent people whose practice or care may be directly affected by the guideline or quality standard.”⁷ They are broadly represented from various sectors. It is believed that the diversity as well as the significant involvement of each stakeholder helps enhance success for acceptance of these quality standards by the public.⁸

There is great transparency and openness not only in the development of a topic accepted by NICE, but also in its final guidelines and recommendations for a quality standard. NICE encourages the public to attend committee meetings to “support NICE’s commitment to having processes in place that are rigorous, open and transparent”⁹ All quality standards that NICE has either developed, is currently developing, or plans to develop are listed for all citizens of England to view on its website.³

For a quality standard to be accepted by NICE, two thirds of the stakeholders must give approval (citation). After this process, an implementation program is submitted to the website to be viewed by all.⁶ The program contains approved quality standards, overview of the disease and potential costs of application. For an implementation program to become standard, the document must “consider the cost of implementing the changes required to achieve the quality standard at a local level and identify where potential cost savings can be made”¹⁰

As an example, NICE has developed an implementation program with quality

standards specific to breast cancer. There are thirteen standards associated with the breast cancer implementation program.¹¹ One of the specific standard quality statements maintains that “people with early invasive breast cancer do not undergo staging investigations for distant metastatic disease in the absence of symptoms.”¹¹ After every quality standard statement, including the one mentioned, an explanation follows describing the evidence-based or cost efficiency data.¹¹ NICE believes that implementing the recommendations based on accredited evidence from the National Health Service and NICE “is the best way to support improvements in the quality of care offered to patients in line with the statements and measures that comprise the NICE quality standards”.¹²

The healthcare system in the United States operates differently than NICE. No implementation programs exist that are similar to those developed by the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence commission. The United States lacks a centralized website where patients can easily view the appropriate treatment for their condition. Instead, patients must Google their condition to self-determine the right course from a variety of treatment options.¹³ Oftentimes, these recommendations are not based on evidence of quality or cost. As a result, patients obtain many conflicting treatment recommendations and options, which have the potential to negatively impact health outcomes in the United States.

NICE has created specific unified screening guidelines for each condition to facilitate disease prevention. These guidelines focus on a variety of recommendations derived from evidence-based data resulting in optimal outcomes for patients at the

best value.¹⁴ All providers in England are expected to follow this single set of guidelines. By simplifying the screening process, patient education is facilitated by clear and transparent recommendations. This streamlining of screening guidelines improves patient adherence and decreases confusion.

A mammogram is an important clinical screening test to detect breast cancer. Great Britain and America differ in their approach to screening guidelines. In England, NICE recommends that women between ages 50 – 70 without risk begin receiving invitations for mammogram screenings every three years.¹⁵ The explanation for this guideline is explained on the NICE website and supported by evidence-based data.

In America, when to initiate breast cancer screenings is confusing due to conflicting guidelines from various competing organizations. For example, the US Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) recommends mammogram screenings every two years for women between the ages of 50 -74.¹⁶ However, the American Cancer Society (ACS) and the American Congress of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (ACOG) recommends starting mammogram screening at age 40 and continuing every year indefinitely as long as the patient is in good health.^{17,18} Screening guidelines that are conflicting in nature lead to confusion and over-utilization of services.

Without a definite guideline by the appropriate health organization, uncertainty exists for both the practitioner and the patient. When unified guidelines are nonexistent, patient education is difficult and potentially compromised. Screening methods and frequency may be unduly influenced by the financial motives of providers or payers rather than what is suggested by sound evidence-based data. This conflicting data can lead to

impaired patient adherence due to lack of clear recommendations.

NICE establishes care pathways organized as flowcharts outlining the steps necessary to adhere to specific quality standard guidelines. The devised pathways are available on the NICE website allowing healthcare providers and patients access to the interactive layout. For example, it is possible to browse the suggested care pathways for a multitude of topics such as advanced breast cancer. According to the guidelines, a patient suspected of having advanced breast cancer should undergo an assessment to determine the presence of this disease.¹⁹ If diagnosed with advanced breast cancer, the care pathway describes the steps of how to manage this disease.¹⁹ These NICE care pathways determine standardized treatments that are based on evidence of quality and cost efficiency.

Unlike England, the United States does not have established uniform pathways regarding set treatment standards. Conflicting guidelines for treatment exist due to lack of a single reliable source. This creates significant confusion for both physicians and patients, resulting in healthcare providers administering varied treatment for the same disease. A lack of consensus causes physicians to rely on prior medical training, personal biases, insurance recommendations and/or financial advantages to guide treatment decisions.

The Quality Outcomes Framework (QOF) implemented by NICE, stresses improving the quality of healthcare practices through an incentive program which financially rewards physicians based on quality of care provided.²⁰ Although NICE does not actually determine QOF indicators, they oversee the development and review

process.²⁰ All QOF indicators reflect the evidence-based, cost-efficient, and high quality of care established by NICE. Physicians are financially rewarded if they meet the established QOF indicators.²⁰ Committees on behalf of the British Medical Association and England's NHS are responsible for deciding which indicators become components of the QOF framework.²⁰ By taking an overseeing role, NICE ensures that QOF indicators reflect the recommendations established by their organization which yield quality care throughout England.

The Quality Outcomes Framework (QOF) is a voluntary financial incentive program that encourages practitioners to provide optimal care. Practices are rewarded points according to successful achievement of QOF indicators.²⁰ This point system reflects the overall performance of a practice in following the established NICE pathways.²⁰ Practices score points when high quality care is provided in the various areas where QOF indicators have been developed. A higher number of points earned correlates to higher financial rewards.

Through the QOF rewards program, there is one uniform incentive standard for physicians. All QOFs are listed on the NICE website creating transparency and lack of misunderstanding for the physician. The results of all medical groups' QOF ratings are published annually, allowing patients as well as the other practices to see who has a higher overall achievement in adhering to QOF indicators.²⁰

An example of a current QOF indicator pertains to Diabetes Mellitus. For this topic, there are specific indicators that aim to improve the management of this condition. One of these specific indicators requires that practices report the "percentage of patients

with diabetes who have a record of a dietary review by a suitably competent professional in the proceeding fifteen months.”²¹ By implementing this indicator, practices will be able to decrease complications associated with diabetes. In conjunction with the indicator, NICE provides key documents that explain reasons why this indicator was developed, how it will impact costs, how equality issues have been considered at each stage of indicator development, and what feedback has been reported.²¹

The Quality Outcomes Framework in England is comparable to the Pay for Performance program in the United States. The Pay for Performance initiative aims to improve the overall cost, quality, and efficiency of healthcare.¹¹ Bonuses are provided to those who achieve defined measurable goals concerning resource use, patient experience, and care outcomes.¹¹ This provides the financial incentive to healthcare providers and hospitals to make the necessary improvements, which are believed to result in optimal outcomes for patients.

However, unlike the QOF program in England, the Pay for Performance program in the United States does not have uniform utilization. State implemented Pay for Performance programs vary with some states not even having these programs.²² The indicators covered vary, leading to confusion by physicians.²² As of 2012, there were more than 40 different private-sector Pay for Performance programs.¹¹ A Pay for Performance program may recommend one set of guidelines to be rewarded, while another may contradict this same guideline. As a result, some physicians have abandoned attempts to follow Pay for Performance programs.²³ Similarly, not all insurance companies participate in Pay for Performance programs. Many times,

participating insurance companies differ on what standards are required to be met for their Pay for Performance program.²⁴ This lack of uniformity in the United States leads to healthcare providers failing to respond to Pay for Performance incentives which prevent potential quality improvements and cost reductions.

A large disparity exists when comparing the equality of medical care delivery between the United States and England. In England, even the poorest individuals can receive quality healthcare since all residents are covered under the National Health Service (NHS). Whether wealthy or poor, all citizens receive the same quality of care due to the guidelines established by NICE for their specific condition. “The United Kingdom exhibits the highest degree of equity regarding access and quality-of-care experiences as well as views of the health system. The relative absence of financial barriers to care in the United Kingdom contributes to these shared experiences.”²⁵

Although the healthcare system in the United States is technologically advanced, the cost of treatment has created access inequality for many citizens. The United States “stands out as having the most severe health care access problems related to cost, the greatest medical expense burdens, and the most pervasive inequities in care between adults with above-average and below-average income.”²⁵ One survey indicates that one out of every five Americans in the United States forgoes medical treatment each year due to finances.²⁵ This inequity to healthcare access is unusual in well-developed and advanced countries. Typically, Americans are covered by private insurance either provided by their employer, or through government programs like Medicare and/or Medicaid.²⁶ Recently, Obamacare has allowed others to purchase medical insurance,

however there is much debate regarding this type of coverage.²⁷ Many who have insurance cannot afford coverage.²⁵ They are unable to afford their medications, co-pays, deductibles, etc. It should not be surprising that out of all the countries in the world, the United States has the most expensive healthcare which often prevents access for many citizens.²⁶

The quality of healthcare in the United States is negatively impacted by significant medical expenses and the presence of conflicting guidelines. Oftentimes, spending more money does not always result in better care. Over treating a condition can reduce the quality of care as it can potentially increase complications. Quality in the United States is further diminished by the variability in treatment due to lack of standardized guidelines.

In the United States, there are no consistent guidelines for treatment of specific conditions. Multiple medical organizations give conflicting guidelines for the same procedure. As a result of a lack of standard treatment guidelines in America, healthcare professionals are often biased in their delivery of care. The frequency and methods of treatments and procedures may be unduly influenced by the financial motives of providers or payers, rather than what is based on sound evidence-based data. Providers many times revert to treating their patients in the manner taught in medical school.

Insurance companies in the United States vary on what they will cover and what treatments are considered necessary. No set standard exists. Procedures and medications covered vary depending on insurance. When purchasing an insurance plan, there is no ability to know what is covered. Since people frequently change plans, insurance companies are only interested in one year of coverage and the benefits for

that particular year.²⁸ Therefore, preventative coverage is usually denied or not emphasized, as it does not benefit the insurance company overall.

Controlling resource allocations increases efficiency and lowers unnecessary cost overhead to support underutilized equipment. NICE establishes recommendations to balance availability of medical resources versus the cost to develop or deploy these assets.²⁹ Instead of suggesting placement of multiple MRI scanners in a populated area, NICE would position the MRI in the location best suited for 100% usage.²⁹ Overall, this method decreases the number of MRI scanners necessary as well as the cost, but also increases their utilization. Savings are achieved from purchasing fewer MRI units and decreasing the number of trained staff necessary to operate these scanners.

The lack of resource allocation control in the United States translates into increased cost overhead and under-utilization of resources. In America, multiple healthcare centers and hospitals may operate MRI technology within close proximity.³⁰ Although this increases convenience for patients, full utilization of these MRI machines is not possible. For example, if there are three MRI units operating within a short distance of each other, each MRI as well as specialized staff will be utilized only one-third of the time. In this example, the cost of providing the same amount of scans would be three times higher in the United States compared to England. In the United States, the cost to support this under-utilized equipment drives up the total cost of healthcare spending. With the development of advanced medications, the cost of providing and receiving care has escalated. These new medications are not only expensive for hospitals and specialists to provide, but also for the patient. Two out of five individuals in the United States do not

fulfill their prescriptions due to financial limitations.²⁵ In England, all medications are covered by the government's national health plan.³¹

The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence commission aims to incorporate evidence-based research within a financially sustainable model. Before more costly drugs are approved for usage, several strict criteria must be met. First, it must be shown that the new drug is superior in effectiveness to less costly alternatives.³² Second, the new drug must provide superior benefit which is significantly meaningful from a quality of life and duration of life basis.³² These benefits must be measurable and sustainable. Thirdly, new medications are evaluated from a value standpoint.³² This ensures the approved medications will be effective, supported by evidence-based data, improve longevity and quality of life, and be affordable.

In England, the benefit of the drug is taken into consideration relative to its incremental cost over existing therapies. Generally, NICE evaluates new treatments in terms of their improvement in quality adjusted life years (QALY).³³ New treatments are only approved if the cost is less than 20,000 – 30,000£ per additional quality adjusted life year gained.²⁹ England provides all citizens with free medical care, so it would not be possible for all drugs to be approved. However, NICE evaluates all medications to determine their efficacy and cost, relative to the currently accepted medication.³⁴ Therefore, money is not wasted on new drugs that have minimal improvements in life expectancy or quality of life.

The Federal Drug Administration (FDA) in America decides whether a new medication will be approved.²⁶ Many new drugs are affirmed by the FDA if they show

clinical benefits and are safe.²⁶ They do not necessarily need to show superiority related to an existing medication, increased duration and quality of life or be more cost-effective.²⁶ This leads to a mass of medications flooding the market creating confusion for both the patient and physician.²⁶ Physicians and patients are led to believe that new medications are better options. This unfortunately is not always true—leading to lack of cost-effective and quality improved medications.

Many drugs approved by the FDA would not be potentially covered by NICE. Abiraterone Acetate, a chemotherapy medication for advanced prostate cancer, is more likely to be covered in the United States as opposed to England. This medication is extremely expensive with limited extensive of life.^{35,36} NICE has a fixed amount of money to cover all citizens of England; therefore, it is not possible for every medication to be covered.³¹ On the other hand, the FDA has allowed the use of Abiraterone in the United States for advanced prostate cancer.¹³ The cost-efficiency of a medication is not a limiting factor for approval by the FDA in the United States. This allows for approval of ever-increasing costly medications without clear benefit over less expensive alternatives.

Abiraterone, when compared to a placebo, has been shown to extend the life of a patient by approximately five months without improving quality.³⁶ However, the monthly cost of this medication in the United States is \$4,638 (UK £2,930).³⁵ In America, the financial burden is placed on the patient. For a five month period, it would cost slightly over \$23,000. Many insurance companies will not cover this medication, but due to lack of clarity, most patients will be unaware of this until the drug is needed. In fact, thirty

percent of all insurance claims in the United States are denied.³¹ Insurance companies that do cover this medication will regain their loss through increased premiums, deductibles, etc.

Administrative costs for providing healthcare are much higher in the United States than in any other country. The US has “by far the highest administrative costs of any health care system on earth.”³¹ In England, all medical treatment is covered, so there are no insurance forms, pre-authorizations, etc. to fill out and submit. However, in the United States, many people are employed to manage insurance claims.³¹ This results in increased costs for healthcare providers, patients, and insurance companies. Administration of insurance claims is a major healthcare cost driver in the United States.

Adopting some elements of the NICE commission generates the potential for the United States to improve healthcare delivery. Standardized care pathways for treatments could be developed rather than having many oftentimes conflicting guidelines. Medical organizations would come together to develop a standardized care pathway for each healthcare topic based on sound evidence-based and cost-effective research. Financial incentives should be provided to the healthcare offices and providers who implement these developed standards. Both insurance companies and the government should reward practices for their efficient, cost-effective, and evidence-based treatment. Also, healthcare in the US has the potential to be improved if there is greater transparency with guidelines. The United States should develop a centralized website where patients can learn about the recommended care pathways for each specific disease.

Major changes in the delivery of healthcare in the United States are critical to

provide sustainable care to its residents. England's NICE organization provides solutions to many of the United States' current healthcare problems. To improve healthcare in the US, flexibility and open-mindedness are essential to move from a costly, inefficient, and complicated system to that of a more transparent and evidence-based system that provides optimal care.

The United States healthcare process seems inferior in quality, in comparison to England's National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE). Instead of having a singular governing healthcare body that produces cost-effective and evidence-based standard care pathways and quality outcomes, the United States has multiple standards with little consensus. As a result, the United States suffers from wide variations in cost, quality, results, and treatments. It is hard to apply standards in the US when there are so many, which are often not evidence-based and do not consider treatment costs. This creates confusion for not only healthcare providers, as well as for patients. The United States has much to learn from England's NICE commission to improve the delivery and quality of care provided.

Works Cited:

1. *About NICE*. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2014. Web. 18 Mar. 2015.
2. *History of NICE*. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2014. Web. 18 Mar. 2015.
3. *Standards and Indicators*. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2014. Web. 18 Mar. 2015.
4. *Quality Standards Topic Library*. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2014. Web. 18 Mar. 2015.
5. *Development of Quality Standard Topics*. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2014. Web. 18 Mar. 2015.
6. <http://www.nice.org.uk/proxy/?sourceUrl=http%3a%2f%2fwww.nice.org.uk%2fmedia%2f175%2f0F%2fQualityStandardsProcessGuideApril2014.pdf>
7. *Stakeholder Registration*. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2014. Web. 18 Mar. 2015.
8. Sorenson, Corinna, Michael Drummond, Panos Kanavos, and Alistair McGuire. "The National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence (NICE): How Does It Work and What Are the Implications for the U.S.?" National Pharmaceutical Council, Apr. 2008. Web. 20 Mar. 2015.
9. *Meetings in Public*. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2014. Web. 18 Mar. 2015.
10. "Implementation Program: Support for commissioners and others using the NICE guidance and quality standard on patient experience in adult NHS Services." *NICE Implementation Programs*. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, Feb. 2012. Web. 19 Mar. 2015.
11. http://www.healthaffairs.org/healthpolicybriefs/brief.php?brief_id=78
12. <http://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/qs12/resources/qs12-breast-cancer-nice-support-for-commissioners-and-others2>
13. <https://www.drugs.com/newdrugs/fda-expands-zytiga-s-late-stage-prostate-cancer-3586.html> FDA Approvals: Expanded Use of Abiraterone for Prostate Cancer *Recommendation Summary*. U.S. Preventive Services Task Force. November 2009.
14. <http://publications.nice.org.uk/how-nice-clinical-guidelines-are-developed-an-overview-for-stakeholders-the-public-and-the-nhs-pmg6f/nice-clinical-guidelines>
15. <http://www.cancerresearchuk.org/about-cancer/type/breastcancer/about/screening/who-is-screened-for-breast-cancer>
16. Recommendations Summary. U.S. Preventive Services Task Force. November 2009
17. <http://www.cancer.org/healthy/findcancerearly/cancerscreeningguidelines/american-cancer-society-guidelines-for-the-early-detection-of-cancer>
18. <http://www.acog.org/About-ACOG/News-Room/News-Releases/2011/Annual-Mammograms-Now-Recommended-for-Women-Beginning-at-Age-40>

19. <http://pathways.nice.org.uk/pathways/>
20. *How We Develop QOF*. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2014. Web. 18 Mar. 2015.
21. *Diabetes Mellitus Indicator: The percentage of patients with diabetes who have a record of a dietary review by a suitably competent professional in the preceding 15 months*. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 1 Aug. 2011. Web. 18 Mar. 2015.
22. http://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&ved=0CB8QFjAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fipro.org%2Fwp-content%2Fuploads%2F2013%2F01%2Fp4pstatemedicaidprogsappendixb1.pdf&ei=2esOVbLHOY3loASXm4KYCQ&usq=AFQjCNGLY5hXNZ84pV28Ud64ThJtalvh_Q&bvm=bv.88_528373,d.cGU
23. Casalino, Lawrence P., et al. "General Internists' Views on Pay-For-Performance and Public Reporting of Quality Scores: A National Survey." *Health affairs* 26.2(2007): 492-9.
24. Congressional Research Service. *Pay-for-Performance in Health Care*. CRS Report., 2006.
25. Cathy Schoen, Robert J. Blendon, Catherine M. DesRoches, and Robin Osborn. 2002. *Comparison of Health Care System Views and Experiences in Five nations*, 2001. New York: The Commonwealth Fund.
26. Feldstein, Paul J. *Health Policy Issues: An Economic Perspective*. Chicago :Washington, DC: Health Administration Press ;AUPHA Press, 2003.
27. Wilensky, Gail R. *The Short Falls of "Obamacare*
28. Fisman, Ray. *Taking Our Medicine: The Bad Economics of Switching Health-Care Plans*. Slate, 7 Sept. 2007. Web. 20 Mar. 2015.
29. "What are the HTA processes in the UK?"
30. *Magnetic Resonance a peer-reviewed, critical introduction*
31. Reid, T. R. *The Healing of America: A Global Quest for Better, Cheaper, and Fairer Health Care* / T.R. Reid. New York: Penguin Press, 2009.
32. "Approving Cancer Drugs in the UK - Where is the Line?" *Progressive Digital Media Healthcare* (incl, Pharmaceuticals, Medical Devices, Hospitals) News 2013.
33. <https://www.nice.org.uk/proxy/?sourceurl=http://www.nice.org.uk/newsroom/features/measuringeffectivenessandcosteffectivenesssthegaly.jsp>
34. <http://scienceblog.cancerresearchuk.org/2014/07/30/will-nices-proposed-reforms-actually-work/>
35. <http://prostatecancerinfolink.net/2012/02/02/nice-initially-refuses-to-cover-cost-of-abiraterone-acetate-for-mcrpc/>
36. <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ta259/chapter/4-consideration-of-the-evidence>